

EFFECT OF A FEED RATION ENRICHED WITH A FOOD ADDITIVE "PROBIOKORM" ON THE DIGESTION PROCESS IN RABBITS

L.U. Erkinova¹, G.T. Abdullayeva², K.I. Hidirov³, M.J. Toshtemirova⁴, G.J. Kutliyeva⁵
Tashkent Branch of the Samarkand State University Veterinary Medicine of Livestock And
Biotechnologies¹

Professor department of Biotechnology of the Tashkent State Technical University named after
Islam Karimov. Uzbekistan, DSc. Tashkent²

Director of the Center for rabbit selection and genetics. Uzbekistan, Tashkent³

Senior Lecturer department of Biotechnology of the Tashkent State Technical University named
after Islam Karimov. Uzbekistan, DSc. Tashkent⁴

Senior Researcher of the Institute of Microbiology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic
of Uzbekistan, PhD. Tashkent⁵

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17129289>

Abstract. *This article studies the changes in the digestive process in rabbits after enriching their diet with the nutritional supplement "Probiokorm". The conducted experiments showed a positive physiological effect of the universal nutritional supplement "ProBioKorm" on the digestive process in rabbits of different ages. The experiments confirmed that the use of these probiotics in the diet is a physiologically active supplement that increases the productivity of rabbits.*

Keywords: *"Probiokorm" nutritional supplement, rabbits, digestion process, productivity, feed consumption, efficiency.*

Introduction

In increasing the productivity of rabbits, their nutritional diet, nutrient environment and the process of digestion of nutrients are of great importance. Several factors can affect the digestion of food in rabbits and the normal functioning of the gastrointestinal system. In particular, it includes stress factors, the composition of the diet, the living environment of rabbits, environmental conditions, genetic factors, the sanitary conditions of the rabbit cage, etc. Adrenal hormones in rabbits, the sensitivity of the nervous system, stress factors negatively affect their digestive processes and slow down the digestion process [2, 8, 6]. One of the best strategies to improve the digestion of rabbits is to add probiotics to their diet, which facilitate the digestion process and contribute to increased productivity. The consumption of probiotics improves the intestinal microflora of rabbits and prevents various pathogenic factors. Probiotics, which are involved in the digestive process, ensure the health of the intestines, preventing the intestinal obstruction that slows down the digestive process. According to Jehl. N and his co-authors, probiotics stimulate the intestinal microflora and are of great importance in the normal physiological development of the intestine [3, 4, 8].

Rabbits are animals with a very complex gastrointestinal tract. The stomach makes up 10-20% of their body weight. The stomach walls are simple and thin, and food is always present in it and is never empty [Chen S, 2006]. In adult rabbits, the low pH of the stomach (1-2) during food

intake helps food to be broken down efficiently. Food usually stays in the stomach of rabbits for 3-6 hours, then gradually passes into the small intestine [7, 9] .

In particular, probiotics can strengthen the immune system against harmful bacteria in the large intestine [5, 6]. Probiotics improve the fermentation process in the stomach. In this process, the bacteria contained in probiotics break down food properly [1, 8]. In addition, the improvement of the digestive process with probiotics is associated with the prevention of inflammation of the stomach. The inflammatory process leads to increased gas in the intestines, in which case probiotics are the most effective method [10, 9].

When studying the effect of probiotics on the digestive process of rabbits, we can conduct scientific analyses based on the feed ration consumed by rabbits, the amount of residual feed, and the amount of excreted feces. For this reason, we studied the effect of a feed ration enriched with the nutritional supplement “ProBiokorm” on the digestive process of rabbits.

Purpose of the research. The effect of a feed ration enriched with the nutritional supplement "ProBiokorm" on the digestive process of rabbits is studied organically.

Research methods and materials. The experiments were conducted in vivo. The rabbits were fed under standard rational vivarium conditions according to their age. The health, growth and development, productivity, fertility and genetic potential of the rabbits in the experiment, and the digestive process depend on the method of timely and full-value feeding.

To conduct the study, a special compound feed recipe was created and feeding standards were developed for the rabbits of the control and experimental groups (Table 1).

Table 1

Accelerate compound feed recipe for rabbits, %

Types of feed	Quantity
Oatmeal	20
Barley grain	18
Wheat bran	11
Sunflower meal	18
Fish meal	3
Clover flour	31
Premix “Universal”	1
Total	100
100 g kombicorm saturation	
Metabolizable energy, kcal	272,9
Nutritional unit, g	0,84
Dry matter, g	88,4
Crude protein, g	22,3
Crude fat, g	4,3
Cellulose, g	16,8
Starch, g	20,3
Calcium, g	7,4
Phosphorus, g	6,7
Sodium, g	4,4

Vitamin A, mg	21,5
Vitamin D, thousand IU	14,3
Vitamin E, mg	9,5

The nutritional value of the compound feed formula presented in Table 1 meets the physiological requirements of rabbits. 100 g of the developed compound feed contains 272.9 kcal of metabolizable energy, 22.3 g of crude protein, 16.8 g of crude cellulose, 7.4 g of Ca²⁺ and 6.7 g of P. The Ca²⁺:P ratio is 1.1:1. The nutritional value of the feed is taken from the data of the A.P. Kalashnikov formula. In the research experiments, mother rabbits were fed a standardized diet. The rabbits of the control group were fed on the basis of the diet adopted on the farm.

The rabbits of the experimental group were fed the probiotic “ProBioKorm” in addition to the main diet (Table 2).

Table 2

Special bacterial strains contained in the feed additive "ProBioKorm"

Microorganisms and their strains present in the dry and liquid form of the probiotic “ProBioKorm”	
1.	- <i>Bacillus subtilis</i> ;
2.	- <i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i> ;
3.	- <i>Lactobacillus paraplantarum</i> ;
4.	- <i>Lactobacillus acidophilus</i> ;
5.	- <i>Pediococcus pentosaceus</i> ;
6.	- <i>Weissella viridescens</i> ;
7.	- <i>Propionibacterium freudenreichii</i> ;
8.	- <i>Bifidobacterium animalis</i> ;
9.	- <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiaye</i> .

The standard for the use of lyophilized biomass of the universal feed additive “ProBioKorm” is 2 g of biomass per 1 kg of feed, and it is recommended to use 2 kg of biomass per 1 ton of feed. In liquid form, it is recommended to use 1-2 l per 1 ton of water. The local probiotic “ProBioKorm” is added to water at the rate of 2 g per 1 rabbit.

The feed additive “ProBioKorm” was developed by employees of the Institute of Microbiology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan in order to improve and enrich the quality of animal feed, improve digestion and absorption of nutrients, prevent various bacterial diseases in animals, and increase productivity.

Obtained results and their analysis. In our experiments we studied the process of digestion of nutrients in the digestive organs of 90-day-old rabbits from 120-day-old mothers who consumed a feed ration enriched with the universal nutritional supplement “ProBioKorm”. In our research work the main goal of selecting 90-day-old rabbits is related to the fact that at this age, rabbits have an accelerated metabolic process. In this process the body directly requires more food, and therefore the amount of food consumed by rabbits increases. 120-day-old mothers are physiologically mature and reproductively fully formed. These physiological indicators also increase the body's tendency to consume more food.

Experiments have scientifically proven that the universal feed additive “ProBioKorm” has a positive effect on the digestive process of rabbits of different ages. In particular, 90-day-old rabbit pups were fed with the same feed ration for the control and experimental groups (the initial feed amount was 210±2.2 g in the control group and 211±2.6 g in the experimental group). Then,

the amount of feed actually consumed by rabbits of both age groups, the amount of residual feed, and the amount of feces excreted by rabbits were studied. In the experiments the feed consumption of rabbit pups that consumed the universal feed additive “ProBioKorm” was observed to be more active than that of the control group. The actual amount of feed consumed by representatives of this group was 170.3 ± 3.2 g, which was 16.4 g more than that of the control. Accordingly, the amount of residual feed was measured. The amount of residual feed in the control group was 44.2 ± 1.3 g, in the experimental group II - 40.2 ± 1.3 . These indicators clearly demonstrate that the universal feed additive "ProBioKorm" had a positive effect on the digestive processes of rabbits and their appetite. In order to reliably study these data, the amount of feces excreted by the experimental animals was analyzed. In the experiments the amount of feces in the animals of the control group I was 41.2 ± 1.8 g, in the experimental group II - 32.8 ± 2.5 g (Fig. 1).

Fig 1. Feed consumption of 90-day-old rabbit babies

Against the background of the above experiments, the feed consumption of 120-day-old rabbits was studied. In these experiments we can see that the universal supplement “ProBioKorm” had a positive effect on the digestive system of both rabbits and mother rabbits. The actual amount of feed consumed by mother rabbits that consumed the “ProBioKorm” feed supplement was 152.8 ± 4.2 g. It was observed that the amount of feed consumed by experimental animals of group II was 4.1 g more than the control. The amount of residual feed in the control group was 41.4 ± 1.3 g, in animals of group II it was 38.2 ± 1.6 g. In the experiments the amount of feces in animals of group I of control was 46.2 ± 1.3 g, in group II of experimental animals it was 39.3 ± 1.8 g (Fig. 2).

The digestibility coefficients of feed were analyzed based on the introduction of the universal supplement “ProBioKorm” into the feed ration of rabbits and its consumption indicators (Figures 3 and 4).

In the experiments, the digestibility of feed in 90-day-old rabbits under the influence of probiotics was 112.7 ± 2.9 g in the control group rabbits, 135.5 ± 2.1 g in the experimental group II, 102.4 ± 4.1 g in the control group rabbits, 110.1 ± 4.9 g in the experimental group II. The digestibility coefficient of feed, in accordance with the above results, was 73.2% in the control group rabbits and 79.5% in the experimental group II, 68.9% in the control group rabbits and 74.2% in the experimental group II in the 120-day-old rabbits.

Fig 2. Feed consumption of 120-day-old mother rabbits

Fig 3. Amount of feed digested in rabbits

Fig 4. Amount of feed digested in rabbits

Conclusion: The experiments conducted showed that the universal feed additive “ProBioKorm” has a positive physiological effect on the digestive process of rabbits of different

ages. The experiments confirmed that the use of these probiotics in the feed ration is a physiologically active additive that increases the productivity of rabbits. The universal feed additive “ProBioKorm” is recommended for use in the rabbit breeding industry.

REFERENCES

1. Abdel-Azeem, A.S., Hassan, A.A., Basyony, M.M. and Abu Hafsa S.H. Rabbit growth, carcass characteristic, digestion, caecal fermentation, microflora, and some blood biochemical components affected by oral administration of anaerobic probiotic (ZAD®)// – Egyptian Journal of Nutrition and Feeds. –2018. –P. 693-710.
2. Alagawany, M., Elnesr, S.S., Farag, M.R., Abd El-Hack, M.E., Barkat, R.A., Gabr, A.A., Foda, M.A., Noreldin, A.E., Khafaga, A.F., El-Sabrou, K., Elwan, H.A. Potential role of important nutraceuticals in poultry performance and health-A comprehensive review// – Research in veterinary science. –2018. –P. 9-29.
3. Cotozzolo E., Cremonesi P., Curone G., Menchetti L., Riva F., Biscarini F., Marongiu M.L., Castrica M., Castiglioni B., Miraglia D., et al. Characterization of Bacterial Microbiota Composition along the Gastrointestinal Tract in Rabbits// – Animals. – 2020. –P. 11:31.
4. Cullere M., Dalle Zotte A. Rabbit Meat Production and Consumption: State of Knowledge and Future Perspectives// – Meat Sci. –2018. –P. 143:137.
5. Gasbarrini G., Bonvicini F., Gramenzi A. Probiotics History// – J. Clin. Gastroenterol. – 2016. –P.116–S119.
6. Lebas F., Coudert P., de Rochambeau H., Thébault R., Rouvier R., Rochambeau H. The Rabbit Husbandry, Health, and Production// Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations-. – Rome, Italy. – 1997. –P.28-39.
7. Mohamed A.F., El-Sayiad G.A., Reda F.M., Ashour E.A. Effects of Breed, Probiotic and Their Interaction on Growth Performance, Carcass Traits and Blood Profile of Growing Rabbits// –Zagazig J. Agric. Res. –2017. -P.215–227.
8. Rotolo L., Gai F., Peiretti P.G., Ortoffi M., Zoccarato I., Gasco L. Live Yeast (*Saccharomyces Cerevisiae* Var. *Boulardii*) Supplementation in Fattening Rabbit Diet: Effect on Productive Performance and Meat Quality// Livest. Sci. – 2014. –P.178–184.
9. Soccol C.R., Vandenberghe L.P., Spier M.R., Medeiros A.B.P., Yamaguishi C.T., De Dea Lindner J., Pandey A., Thomaz-Soccol V. The Potential of Probiotics A Review// Food Technol. Biotechnol. –2010. –P. 413–434.
10. T.M. EL Gusbi, H.M. Gado , and H.M. Metwally. Eeffect of probiotic on in vitro rabbit cecum fermentation, chemical analysis and in vitro digestibility //–Egyptian J. Nutrition and Feeds. –2024. –P.175-185